

COMPARISON OF DAMAGE CHARACTERISTICS OF ADHESIVELY BONDED AND RIVET-CONNECTED EVTOL WING UNDER BIRD-STRIKE

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Motivation

Comparison of damage results at the parts of the rivet-connected and the adhesively bonded configurations of a composite eVTOL wing leading edge.

Investigation of the best absorbent core material to be implemented to develop the lightest composite eVTOL leading edge which can stand against bird impact.

Figure – 1 Airbus nextGen (eVTOL)

Introduction and Motivation

EASA CS 25.631

648.2 KPH

Max. Cruise Speed (KPH) vs Company - eVTOL

Figure - 2 Comparison of eVTOL Cruise Speeds

Introduction and Motivation

Figure – 3 Hugoniot Pressure

Figure – 4 Shock Phases

Numerical Models & Cases

Adhesively Bonded and Rivet-connected eVTOL Wing Under Bird-Strike

Figure – 5 Skin, honeycomb and auxiliary spar attachment configurations at the leading edge of the wing, The rivet-connected configuration

Figure – 6 Skin, honeycomb and auxiliary spar attachment configurations at the leading edge of the wing, The bonded configuration

Material Properties & Test Campaign (UD Skin & Aramid Core)

- ASTM C365 - Applied Force vs Displacement

0.5 min/mm 6.35 x 50 x 50 mm

Figure – 8 Core Specimen for C365

Figure – 9
Core Specimen for C365

- UD; Stacking: [0/90/-45/45]3s UD M91/IM7 Each ply: 0.184mm (24 plies Facing & 24 plies Backing)

Material Properties & Test Campaign (UD Skin & Aramid Core)

- ASTM C364 5 min/mm 6.35 x 50 x 50 mm

* Experiment-3 is failed because of stability problems. Therefore, Experiment-4 supersedes, Experiment-3.
** Experiment-5 is failed because of stability problems. Therefore, Experiment-6 supersedes, Experiment-5.

Loading Condition – Normal Impact

• The Impact Condition vs Time

[t, mm, N, s, mJ, MPa]

Figure – 13 X Velocity of The Bird and The Wing Model

FEA Results 1st Principal Stress Distribution, Lower Attachment

FEA Results - 1st Principal Stress

Figure – 15 1st Principal Stress Distribution at The Attachment Parts and Spar of The Rivet Connected Case

Figure – 16 1st Principal Stress Distribution at The Attachment Parts and Spar of The Adhesively Bonded Case

Tsai-Wu Failure Theory $\left(\frac{1}{X_t} - \frac{1}{X_c}\right) \sigma_1 + \left(\frac{1}{Y_t} - \frac{1}{Y_c}\right) \sigma_2 + \frac{\sigma_1^2}{X_t X_c} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y_t Y_c} + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S^2} + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 = \text{Failure Index} \dots (1)$

X_t, X_c, Y_t and Y_c
Material properties

σ_1, σ_2, S and τ_{12}
FEA results

F_{12}
Numeric parameter

$$\left[\frac{\sigma_1^2}{X_t X_c} + \frac{\sigma_2^2}{Y_t Y_c} + 2F_{12} \sigma_1 \sigma_2 + \frac{\tau_{12}^2}{S^2} \right] SR^2 + \left[\sigma_1 \left[\frac{1}{X_t} - \frac{1}{X_c} \right] + \sigma_2 \left[\frac{1}{Y_t} - \frac{1}{Y_c} \right] \right] SR = 1$$

Shear Stress & Safety Reserve Results

Table – 1 Shear Stress Results at The Attachment Parts and Spar of The Adhesively Bonded Case						
Time [ms]	Rivet- connected	Adhesively Bonded	Rivet- connected	Adhesively Bonded	Rivet- connected	Adhesively Bonded
	Upper Attachment	Upper Connection	Lower Attachment	Lower Connection	Spar	Spar
2.5	52.9	29.3	51.3	37.0	36.2	9.4

[MPa]

Table – 2 Safety Reserve Results at The Attachment Parts and Spar of The Adhesively Bonded Case						
Time [ms]	Rivet- connected	Adhesively Bonded	Rivet- connected	Adhesively Bonded	Rivet- connected	Adhesively Bonded
	Upper Attachment	Upper Connection	Lower Attachment	Lower Connection	Spar	Spar
2.5	9.56e-3	5.3e-3	9.27e-3	6.69e-3	6.54e-3	1.7e-3

[Unitless]

Concluding Remarks & Future Work

- Lower principal stress and shear stress results are evaluated for the adhesively bonded case. Moreover, the safety reserve results are lower than the rivet-connected case. However, both cases are beyond safe region. Therefore, the following tasks will be performed as a future work to compare these cases and make a reliable comment;
- Results under various stacking configurations
- Investigation of connector fails (i.e Pull-through mode)

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Thank you!

Questions & Answers